

“Women empowerment through PM Ujjwala Yojana”

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Abstract:

With the objective of conservation of environment and women empowerment through Improvement health. The scheme was launched on 1st May 2016 in Ballia, Uttar Pradesh by Hon'ble Prime Minister of India, Shri. Narendra Modi. Alternatively, this came will be save the natural resources which are related to the energy it will be helpful to in sustainable development in India due to its important is very strong in the developing India. With the objective of conservation of environment and women empowerment through Improve health. In this respective research study is very important for the selected area which is defined Jamkhed Tehsil in Ahmednagar district, in this research area more women using the traditional energy resources for the cooking and allied work so that pm is playing vital role in this area. how many Women are benefited by the scheme and what is the importance of its. Is this game helpful to improvement in women health and beside of it conserve the traditional resources like firewood, Kerosene, fuel etc.

In rural India, firewood and chips was used in 2009-10 as principal source of energy for cooking by more than three-quarters (76.3%) of households, LPG by 11.5%, and dung cake by 6.3%. About 1.6% of rural households did not have any arrangement for cooking. The remaining households used other sources, including kerosene (0.8%) and coke/coal (0.8%). Above-described situation is damages to environmental health. Due to the subsidy not only, real income rises but also it helps to improve environmental quality. Due to uses of traditional fire cooking energy resources women are affected By affected by smoke of wooden fire and they are losing good health as well as lost the more time for cooking due to this scheme women save their time and save their health.

Key words: PM Ujjwala Yojana, real income, environmental protection, women health, Time and money saving, subsidy.

Introduction:

When we comparatively think about consumption of energy resources traditional energy resources uses like firewood, Dung cake, Crop residue it is more than uses of LPG or new energy

resources. It is directly affected to women's health as well as environment. It means there is need to raise awareness among the rural people about LPG uses.

Save Time and money of particular families and protect to environment with this major purpose The scheme was launched on 1st May 2016 in Ballia, Uttar Pradesh by Hon'ble Prime Minister of India, Shri. Narendra Modi. With the major purpose as a protection to women's health and save their time and money as well as protect to environment. In May 2016, Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas (MOPNG), introduced the 'Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana' (PMUY) as a flagship scheme with an objective to make clean cooking fuel such as LPG available to the rural and deprived households which were otherwise using traditional cooking fuels such as firewood, coal, cow-dung cakes etc.

Usage of traditional cooking fuels had detrimental impacts on the health of rural women as well as on the environment.

On 7th September 2019, Hon'ble Prime Minister of India handed over the 8th Crore LPG connection in Aurangabad, Maharashtra. The target under the scheme was to release 8 Crore LPG Connections to the deprived households by March 2020. The release of 8 Crore LPG connections under the scheme has also helped in increasing the LPG coverage from 62% on 1st May 2016 to 99.8% as on 1st April 2021. Ujjwala 2.0 Additional allocation of 1.6 Crore LPG Connections under PMUY Scheme with special facility to migrant households. The

scheme was launched in Mahoba, Uttar Pradesh by Hon'ble Prime Minister of India, Shri. Narendra Modi. Total Connections Released under Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana as on 31 May 2023 were 95,859,418 and Connections released under Ujjwala 2.0 as on 31 May 2023, were 15,994,338. Presently The CCEA has raised the subsidy from ₹ 200 per cylinder to ₹300 for up to 12 refills per year, Mr. Thakur told the media. He, however, did not reveal the additional subsidy outgo the move would entail. Through this research Paper we can find out the effectiveness of the PM Ujjwala scheme at Jamkhed tehsil.

Due to the using of traditional energy resources in domestic purpose specially cooking by women they are losing their time and energy to collect Fairwood for cooking and due to the using traditional energy resources more health problem in this respective pm Ujjwala Yojana launched by government in 2016 due to his scheme women will get relaxation from troubling traditional energy resources and they are saving their time and physical energy which is distributed for collecting energy resources like firewood, Kerosene etc. as well as it is helpful to healthy environment. Jamkhed Tehsil is one of the semi-rural areas in this area women are using the traditional energy resources for the cooking. How many women or families benefited by this scheme? And how they feel after that adopting the scheme? What are the expectations from the benefited women in futures to this scheme? it will be find and suggested through this research study. Eligibility criteria to avail connection under Ujjwala 2.0, Applicant woman only must have attained 18 years of age, There should not be any other LPG connection from any OMC in the same household, Adult woman belonging to any of the following categories – SC, ST, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (Gramin), Most Backward Classes (MBC), Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY), Tea and Ex- Tea Garden tribes, Forest Dwellers, People residing in Islands and River Islands, enlisted under SECC Households (AHL

TIN) or any Poor Household as per 14-point declaration. Jamkhed Tahasil has total 184,167 Population and it divided into 5 Panchayat Gan-Aarangaon, Javala, Kharada, Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed and Sakat.

Objectives:

1. To find out effectiveness of pm Ujjwala Yojana.
2. To find out how women are satisfaction by this scheme.
3. To raise the awareness among the women to uses of LPG.

Hypotheses:

1. PM Ujjwala Yojana is helpful to improve women's health as well as time and money saving.
2. PM Ujjwala Yojana is helpful regarding to the conserve natural energy resources which are using by women for cooking as well as helpful to saving women's efforts.
3. PM Ujjwala Yojana is helpful to sustainable development.

Sampling:

Probability Sampling Method (Lottery Method) used for Sampling. Jamkhed Tahasil is divided into 5 Panchayat Gan-Aarangaon, Javala, Kharada, Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed and Sakat. For the Research Paper 50 sample will be collected. Out of this sample 50 sample collected from each Panchayat (5) [10 X 5 = 50] with the help of using the systematic sample.

Methodology:

For the Research Paper study there will be using the survey method in this method researcher will be collect the data from different gas agencies and after Collecting benefited women's list it will be structured systematically and for the collecting sample will be used the lottery method.

For the analysis of collecting data researcher will be used different statistical tools like correlation regression average and SPSS.

Data Analysis: collected data is tabulate and create tables for analysis. With the help of tabulated data there is used statistical tools as well as created graphs for analysis.

Table: 1. Age classification of Consumer

Panchayat Gan / Age of Consumer (Year)	18-38	39-59	60+	Total
Aarangaon	7	2	1	10
Javala	4	4	2	10
Kharada	8	2	0	10
Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed	8	1	1	10
Sakat	5	3	2	10
Total	32	12	6	50
Percentage %	64	24	12	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire

According to Pm Ujjwala Yojana, Age of women consumer should be more than 18 years. It means another side this scheme is promote adult marriage. Age wise classification is classified in the above table No. 1 of Consumer. There is a major consumer are included in Age group of 18-38,

Which are 32 (64%) out sample. It means Youth women are aware to Consumption of PM Ujjwala Yojana as well as benefits of LPG gas. the proportion of Age group of 39-59 and 60+, is 12 (24%) and 6 (12%) respectively. It means we have to increase awareness among the Age group of 39-

59 and 60+ about uses of PM Ujjwala Yojan.
 The more consumers are involved in the

PM Ujjwala Yojan, the more the consumer will
 benefit and the environment will also be protected.

Source: composited Graph on the bases of questionnaire

Above Graph is clearly shown that the consumer of Poor Households are least part of PM Ujjwala Yojana consumer. Another side SC and ST Consumer is greatest part of PM Ujjwala Yojana

their proportion is 44% and 34% Respectively. It means if we have to increase beneficiary for Poor Household, we have to increase subsidy under PM Ujjwala Yojana for inclusion of Poor Household.

Table: 2. Period of consumption (Year)

	Period (Year)				
	7	5	3	2	Total
Total	4	8	15	23	50
Percentage %	8	16	30	46	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire

PM Ujjwala Yojana launched by government in 2016 science to this year to till date seven years completed. 8 % of sample of consumers is taking benefits of PM Ujjwala Yojana science 7 years. 46% Consumers who are consuming PM

Ujjwala Yojana their consuming period is last 2 years. It means after the launching the scheme Pm Ujjwala Yojana it had taken some time to spread in the Society.

Table: 3. Family members

Panchayat Gan / No. of cylinder	2	3	4	5	Total
Aarangaon	2	3	4	1	10
Javala	1	3	5	1	10
Kharada	2	2	5	1	10
Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed	0	3	4	3	10
Sakat	3	1	6	0	10
Total	8	12	24	6	50
Percentage %	16	24	48	12	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire

In the table No. 3 Family members are included who have been consumers of PM Ujjwala Yojana Scheme. If family has More members these families will consume more cylinders. In this case Families demanded more cylinders. But in the

Scheme Maximum 12 cylinders provided under subsidy per year. There are 6 (12%) families find who has 5 members in family. Absolutely their demand of cylinder should be more then less family members.

Table: 4. Annual consumption of Cylinders

Panchayat Gan/ No. of cylinder	8	10	12	14	Total
Aarangaon	3	1	4	2	10
Javala	3	4	2	1	10
Kharada	2	1	4	3	10
Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed	1	5	3	1	10
Sakat	5	2	1	2	10
Total	14	13	14	9	50
Percentage %	28	26	28	18	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire

In the table No. 4 is display the annual consumption of cylinders by family. Accordion to PM Ujawala Yojana every year 12 cylinders provided with subsidy by Government. In the Sample area there are 9 families who are consuming 14 cylinders in the year. Regarding to table No. 5, total 5 families who has five family members Those demand of cylinders is more than 12, it is 14

cylinders per year more two cylinders has not subsidy. Due to Non subsidy cylinders real income if family is reducing. So that poor families facing more economic problems. Those families have minimum members those demand of cylinder is more in the condition of other uses of cylinder like non cooking function.

Table: 5. Benefits by PM Ujjwala Yojan

Benefits by PM Ujjwala Yojan					
Panchayat Gan	Money saving	time saving	to avoid smoke	All	Total
Aarangaon	0	0	0	10	10
Javala	0	0	0	10	10
Kharada	0	0	0	10	10
Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed	0	0	0	10	10
Sakat	0	0	0	10	10
Total	0	0	0	50	50
Percentage %	0	0	0	100	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire

In the Table No. 5. Tabulated the Benefits by PM Ujjwala Yojan Whole sample or sub universe is economic and non-economic benefits consuming.

Like; Money saving, time saving, protection from smoke etc. 100% population of sample was choosing option 'D'

Table: 6. Satisfaction from PM Ujjwala

Panchayat Gan	Satisfaction form PM Ujjwala		
	YES	NO	TOTAL
Aarangaon	8	2	10
Javala	7	3	10
Kharada	10	0	10
Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed	9	1	10
Sakat	10	0	10
Total	44	6	50
Percentage %	88	12	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire

In the above Table No. 6, classified data regarding to Satisfaction form PM Ujjwala Yojana. In this table 88% population of sample satisfied

from this scheme. But remaining 12% Population not satisfied. They have more acceptation from Scheme.

Table: 7. Reduction of firewood

Panchayat Gan	YES	NO	TOTAL
Aarangaon	10	00	10
Javala	10	00	10
Kharada	10	00	10
Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed	10	00	10
Sakat	8	2	10
Total	50	2	50
Percentage %	96	4	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire means this practice is becoming as a protecting to environment.

In table No. 7. Population of sample is 96% answered that, due to consumption of PM Ujjwala Yojana uses of firewood is reduced in the cooking. It

Table: 8. Acceptation form PM Ujjwala Yojana

Panchayat Gan	Increase the no. of Cylinders	Increase subsidy	All	TOTAL
Aarangaon	0	0	10	10
Javala	0	0	10	10
Kharada	0	1	9	10
Nagar Panchayat Jamkhed	4	0	6	10
Sakat	0	0	10	10
Total	4	1	45	50
Percentage %	8	2	90	100

Source: composited table on the bases of questionnaire

In the above Table No. 8 classified Acceptation form PM Ujjwala Yojana. 2% families given preference to Increase subsidy. 8% families given preference to Increase the no. of Cylinders And 90% Population has more acceptations from PM Ujjwala Yojana. Increase the no. of Cylinders, increase subsidy. Due to these acceptations real income of families will increased.

After the calculated Correlation between Annual consumption of Cylinders and Family members is positive and strong (0.573155) it's mean is yearly consumption of cylinder is increasing with members. Due to over consumption (12 cylinders) family has to more income expenditure on non-subsidy cylinders. It is affected to real income is decreasing. poor people carry more Burdon of non-subsidy cylinder.

There is negative and weak correlation (-0.221403721) find between Satisfaction and acceptations from PM Ujjwala Yojana. it indicated that high acceptations from PM Ujjwala Yojana of people.

Conclusion:

1. The proportion of Age group of 39-59 and 60+, is 12 (24%) and 6 (12%) respectively. It means we have to increase awareness among the Age group of 39-59 and 60+ about uses of PM Ujjwala Yojan.
2. After the launching the scheme Pm Ujjwala Yojana it had taken some time to spread in the Society.
3. less beneficiary of Poor Household, we have to increase subsidy under PM Ujjwala Yojana for inclusion of Poor Household.
4. Those families have minimum members those demand of cylinder is more in the condition of other uses of cylinder like non cooking function.
5. 100% population of sample is beneficial and satisfactory.
6. Due to consumption of PM Ujjwala Yojana uses of firewood is reduced in the cooking. It means this practice is becoming as a protecting to environment.
7. Due to increase subsidy real income of families will be increased.
8. Correlation between Annual consumption of Cylinders and Family members is positive and strong (0.573155) it's mean is yearly consumption of cylinder is increasing with members. There is negative and weak correlation (-0.221403721) find between Satisfaction and acceptations from PM Ujjwala Yojana.

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